

COMPOSITE STRUCTURES FOR LARGE ASYMMETRIC PAYLOAD FAIRINGS

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SUMMARY: The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) has undertaken a research program to assess the utility of developing mission specific fairings to support unique and high-cost, high-risk payloads for the United States Department of Defence (DOD). Generally, AFRL has observed that the largest, most costly payloads for space launch frequently must deal with elevated mission risks because their launch geometry must conform to pre-qualified, general purpose, fairing geometries. The approach presented below poses new challenges for development of large composite structures and distributes risk more equitably between launch vehicle components and spacecraft developers.

KEYWORDS: Asymmetric, payload, fairing, aero-stability, acoustic mitigations, mechanical isolation, low-cost composites, rapid tooling

INTRODUCTION

The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) is committing increasing research funding to investigation of more efficient means of developing unique large composite structures to support volume constrained payloads and other large launch vehicle components. This research has evolved over the past five years through investment in composites technology development through in-house research, Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) contracts, and cooperation with major composite manufacturers and launch vehicle contractors. The investigations have included numerous assessments of advanced composite fabrication systems (Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) techniques, ultrasound consolidation and thermoplastic welding). New tooling techniques for rapid, low-cost composite fabrication with limited production goals, unique acoustic mitigation systems integral to the composite fairing, and improved mechanical isolations systems are also under development.

A principal motivation for this research is to develop an alternative paradigm for spacecraft developer and launch vehicle contractor interaction. Most frequently spacecraft developers are unaware of the range of limitations or flexibilities for launch vehicle constraints. Launch vehicle contractors typically publish “user manuals” for pre-qualified fairing designs. A few minor modifications can usually be accomplished to support mission requirements, such as moving access doors or modifying acoustic mitigations systems. However the general impression conveyed to the experimenter is that major modifications such as shape changes are not practical and non-negotiable. This perceived limitation can impact the largest payloads very significantly and can, for instance, result in attempts to implement odd shaped mirror systems (elliptical perimeters) or folding mirror segments. The folding mirror option

presents great technical challenges to accurate deployment on orbit with micro-radian tolerances often being imposed.

AFRL is proposing the consideration of rapid development of mission unique fairings for payloads meeting certain qualifications. One of these is a large payload volume requirement, as for large optical systems or folding radar arrays. High technical risk introduced by requirements to accommodate fairing constraints can justify risk balancing through fairing modifications or redesign. Adequate program development funding resources to allow consideration of fairing development risks versus spacecraft development risk are essential. Programs costing over about \$500M USD probably meet the final criteria. In pursuit of this goal, AFRL has sponsored two workshops to discuss Large Fairing development and present results of AFRL sponsored research. This paper will synthesize the major findings of these workshops with emphasis on impacts to composite technology needs.

ASYMMETRIC FAIRING DEVELOPMENT

Current Large Fairing Designs

The largest pre-qualified fairings in use by US launch vehicle contractors have a cylindrical cross section diameter of 5 meters. The largest US launch vehicles, Atlas V and Delta IV, could reasonably handle load generation for fairings of larger diameter, up to perhaps 7 or 8 meter. Typically, larger fairings can introduce ground handling and infrastructure conflicts such illustrated in Fig. 1. The Boeing Lift Tower for elevating the payload, adapter, and fairing into position on the launch vehicle has an approximate constraint of 5 meters square. To modify this structure would impact numerous other launch systems and result in total launch pad modification costs approaching \$1B USD. Note, however, that by simply moving some corner bracing in this structure, a free dimension approaching 10 meters becomes available.

Fig. 1: Boeing Payload/Fairing Tower

Three Proposed Geometries to Support Launch of a 10 meter Diameter Optic

Over the past two years AFRL has supported work by the Boeing Company, Nielsen Engineering and Research (NEAR), and ATA Engineering (ATA) to develop alternative designs and preliminary assessments of three fairing concepts to support launch of a fictitious 10 meter optic experiment. Fig. 3 illustrates the mirror geometry prescribed by AFRL for these exercises. In addition to mirror dimensional constraints, a moderate payload mass and supplemental volume to support an operating experiment were included. Each contractor approached the design process in a different way.

Fig. 2: Reference Mirror Geometry

For instance, the Boeing concept (Fig. 4) is based on cutting wing ports in an existing composite fairing design and adding blunt low-lift lobes to accommodate mirror protrusions. This lobe configuration was analyzed as a simple sandwich panel and the launch induced stresses were seen to be quite manageable. This was an intuitive, one iteration design effort with limited funding. Basic launch vehicle stability was seen to be somewhat beyond the control limits of the Delta IV, but Boeing judged the design to be close enough to be made workable with additional modifications.

Fig. 3: Boeing Fairing Configuration

Nielsen Engineering started with a clean slate and used an in-house aero-optimization routine to iteratively converge to an optimal shape to maximize overall launch vehicle stability. This technique resulted in reliable overall launch vehicle stability with objectives set by Boeing for the Delta IV. One fairing configuration of many analyzed is shown in Fig. 4 and highlights a potential control feature for shock separation. Fig. 5 compares stability at multiple angles of attack for the Boeing 5 meter fairing and a Nielsen configuration. The new design stability can be made stable and linear with increasing angle of attack, but the response is much more sensitive to Mach number. Shape optimization must be driven by multiple angle of attack constraints to obtain this behaviour. Fig. 6 demonstrates acceptable design strength for a 2.5 cm thick honeycomb shell and two plies of IM7-8552 woven pre-preg.

Fig. 4: Representative Nielsen Fairing Configuration

Fig. 5: Boeing 5 meter and Nielsen 10 meter LV Stability Comparison

Fig. 6: Nielsen Composite Structure Analysis--Tsai-Wu Failure Criteria

The ATA fairing design seeks to minimize aero loading by inducing a wind vane effect to supplement launch vehicle control authority. Shown in Fig 7, this geometry was evaluated primarily by optimizing these control forces at the base of the fairing. Shape optimization techniques were applied to this design as well. This fairing was also assessed structurally. Monocoque and sandwich panel variants were analyzed for response to aero loads. In general only limited areas of the structure saw high stresses.

Fig. 7: ATA Fairing Concept

The basic result of each of these preliminary studies was that no physical limit has yet been found. Each contractor completed only a limited study, and AFRL has subsequently decided to award two SBIR Phase II contracts. One team led by NEAR will work with Boeing and other contractors. Another led by ATA will team with Lockheed Martin and other contractors. There many issues for aero stability and control that must be resolved over the course of these two year studies leading to preliminary system designs and wind tunnel testing. If the aerodynamic issues prove tractable, there are a number of issues relating to composite design and fabrication we must resolve as well.

Composite Research Needed to Support the New Designs

At this point of preliminary assessment, none of the potential designs appear to be strongly challenged by strength and buckling issues. Fairings are not typically subjected to very high stresses by aero loads and this trend may hold for the asymmetric designs. However other system issues will become amplified by these designs.

These are large fairings with large skin surfaces and weight must be held in check to prevent unwanted payload mass limitations. This low mass requirement has a major impact on acoustic transmission. Additionally, the non-cylindrical shaping creates large flat spots on the skin, which can result in troublesome, low frequency resonances. Low frequency acoustic noise is a common source of payload damage during launch. AFRL is investigating multiple means of building composite structure isolation systems into the walls of the fairing, as well as targeting specific low frequency resonances by active methods (see Fig 8).

Fig. 8: Structural ChamberCore and Active VibroAcoustic Device (AVAD)

By even the most optimistic accounts, these new fairing shapes will probably result in a somewhat rougher ride for the payload, unless improved damping or isolation can be provided

to counter flutter and other aero-instabilities. AFRL and Boeing have attempted to incorporate viscoelastic damping layers into small test fairings, but without success (see Fig 9). Curing problems have led to wrinkling and disbonding of viscous layers in past attempts. More work is needed in this area.

Fig. 9: Viscoelastic damping concept

In the past AFRL has developed general purpose, passive damping for payload to composite adapter isolation. In the case of a large optic experiment, a large composite adapter will be required to distribute support to the lightweight optic. The fairing may also support the optic through some isolation system in contact with the mirror. At a minimum, isolation of the fairing from the launch vehicle could be useful to limit payload vibration. In the past these isolation systems have been aluminium and elastomer fabrications (see Figures 9 *AFRL/Boeing DUST Program* & 10 *CSA patented isolation system*). With larger isolator contact surfaces, it could be wise to investigate alternative composite fabrications instead. This work has not been attempted at this scale to our knowledge.

Fig 10: Typical passive isolation system

Just the fabrication of such a large, awkward structure requires new thought. One of the objectives of payload specific fairing development would be to hold the design of a new fairing for a year or two in the evolution of a major payload to allow spacecraft designers to better assess practical shape constraints of the payload. This could still leave 4 to 6 years to design and test a new fairing. Rapid prototyping measures would be of immense help in meeting these schedules. AFRL is teaming with Alliant Space Structures (ATK) and others to attempt rapid, low-cost tool development for major launch vehicle components. Carbon foam and all-composite tooling options are under consideration for one such structure now. These tools can not be budgeted for amortization over tens of launches. The composite tool must be cheap and light to hold down handling effort during fabrication and reduce costs of other support tools.

AFRL funded one study based on large cylindrical sections two years ago. After evaluating several new composite fabrication technologies to address the need to avoid current 5 meter

diameter limits on autoclave dimensions, ATK finally recommended an oven-cured, hand-placed, pre-preg cloth fabrication process. They justified their findings based on costs and out-times associated with tape placing such large acreages of material. ATK is currently designing a larger fairing for the Peacekeeper based Minotaur IV launch vehicle using the oven cured hand-placed pre-preg. The base of the fairing, or boat tail, is more highly loaded and will use a VARTM process developed by Webcore to produce an internal truss structure around individual foam cores (see Figure 12). With changes in shape to flatter geometries, tool handling and access for hand placement are much more difficult, and options for tape placement are being re-evaluated. Current industry averages for tape placement rates of 8 lineal feet per second need to be improved significantly. Factors of 2 to 5 times, or tapes of up to 12" width, should be considered to limit out-time. Additionally, the advanced grid-system configuration developed by AFRL for the Minotaur II fairing is also being considered for these large fairings. The placement system is versatile and progress has been made in placing the ribs using ultrasound consolidation, which can eliminate the need for autoclave curing (see Figure 13).

Fig. 12: Preliminary Minotaur IV Large Fairing Boat Tail

Fig: 13: Minotaur IV Large Fairing and Foster Miller UTL process

Thermal protection requirements for typical medium to large fairing systems are not as aggressive as typical re-entry vehicle requirements. Insulation is usually provided in the form of cork sheeting bonded to the outer composite skin of the fairing (see Fig 14). The cork mass is significant (about 600 to 1000 lbs for a 10 meter fairing), requires high skill and labour, and is expensive to apply. The unusual double curvatures of an asymmetric fairing will contribute to the difficulty of meeting production deadlines and mass objectives. Ideally a thin, lightweight, spray-on, thermal isolation coating might be sought for this application.

Fig. 14: Typical fairing cork application

CONCLUSIONS

The concepts for large, mission unique fairings presented in this paper are in early stages of aerodynamic design and validation. Multiple preliminary studies have been conducted and all point with some significant hope to a useful final product. Two Phase II SBIR efforts are just beginning and should bear fruit in about 24 months. To keep this effort on track beyond that milestone, several additional technical issues need to be confronted. There is a need for improved low-cost (low-production) tooling and high volume out-of-autoclave fabrication processes. New, more severe acoustic and mechanical vibration environments may result requiring improved technology. Thermal insulation technology for fairings has not changed significantly in 50 years and should be upgraded if possible to accommodate fast, safe application and reduced mass.

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